

Rural Women and Human Rights: A Sociological Analysis

Paper Id : 18349 Submission Date : 05/01/2024 Acceptance Date : 11/01/2024 Publication Date : 15/01/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10605224

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/anthology.php#8>

Sonu Puri

Assistant Professor
Sociology
Government Girls Degree
College, Bangar,
Kannauj, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

Human rights are fundamental rights that every person has regardless of their race, gender, and national or ethnic origin, color, religion, language or any other status. To reduce the likelihood of tyranny and to advance justice and well-being in society everyone should be aware of what human rights are. Human rights awareness, comprehension and application can empower individuals, advance solutions for particular issues and thereby lessen conflict in society. Women's ability to receive equal treatment and appropriate respect within the current human rights framework is severely hampered by the fact that most human rights documents define women in terms of their childbearing and domestic duties, and the family which is frequently seen as a breeding ground for violence, injustice and oppression for many women continues to be referred to as the fundamental unit of society. The goal of the current study was to ascertain the level of knowledge regarding rights among rural women. Using observation, interview, schedule information was gathered for this objective.

Keywords Human Rights, Provisions, Legislations, Gender Equality, Development.

Introduction

"Human Rights are not a privilege conferred by government. They are very human being's entitlement by virtue of his humanity"..... Mother Teresa

Human Rights are international phenomena because they have become ingrained in our society over time. Because of the presence of Human Rights (HR), we are able to live as humans on this planet. The need of mankind for a life that aspects and upholds each person's intrinsic worth and dignity forms the foundation of fundamental freedoms. Each of us has needs and rights, which we must respect and protect. In India women are actively involved in achieving all human rights, including civil, political, economic, social and cultural freedoms, on an equal footing with men. After years of battle, these rights for women have finally been declared an inherent component of human rights for everybody. The Indian women for a very long time, society have been subjected to abuse, humiliation torture, and exploitation at the hands of their male counterparts. The most dangerous kind of violence is sexual assault against women. Women experience sexual assault at home, at work, at markets and in other settings as well. Indian women have historically suffered greatly from a variety of social, economic and political disadvantages including economic dependence, patriarchal family structures, ideal of daughter noble marriages, child marriages, joint family systems, illiteracy and various forms of violence both inside the home and outside in the streets and workplaces. But because they are living things with basic human rights, they require protection under the law. In order to define one's own independence one must also be aware of how to apply the law and the many legal protections for women's rights in India where the Indian constitution is a key component of all.

A global campaign to elevate women's position has given rise to the phrase "women's human rights" and the associated practices. These are always changing products of this movement. Throughout the 1980s and 1990s, women's movements developed networks and coalitions to raise awareness of the challenges that women deal with on a daily basis as well as well the importance of women's experiences in relation to political, social, economic and environmental issues. Within the developing worldwide women's movement, the phrase "women's human rights" has functioned as a hub for praxis, meaning the creation of political plans influenced by the interplay between intellectual understandings

and tangible political actions. Furthermore, women can now acquire the political skills required for the twenty-first century through the critical tools, coordinated activism, and wide-based International networks that have developed around movements for women's human rights.

Aim of study

The objective of this study is to determine how much rural women are aware of their rights?

Review of Literature

Roy (2003) examined the various aspects of women's rights, including their political and reproductive rights, as well as their rights as young women and children. Women frequently deal with issues such as domestic violence, underage marriages, prostitution, rape and sexual assault. Violations of fundamental human rights resulted from these problems. Traditional domestic roles for women in India are more constrained. Instead of having access to social, economic and political rights that are tied to the general public; they tend to be more restricted to private matters. **Sammiah and Mahavi (2005)** concentrated on how women employed in unorganized sectors are paid. From TamilNadu's Sivagangai area, 420 female construction workers were selected as a sample because these unorganized women are compelled to do so by their poverty and illiteracy, they work for very little pay. They have a difficult life because they are construction workers. At the construction site, they must deal with diseases, injuries and sexual harassment. Even after working for many years, they still lag behind males in skill levels and are unskilled. **Sangeeta Sinha (2011)** talked about in detail that due to Tunisia's Arab heritage, women were not allowed to attend school, were restricted to the home and were required to wear veils before the country gained its freedom. Women in Tunisia made significant progress in obtaining more rights. The state has accepted responsibility for bringing about the required and desirable changes in human rights. **Rastogi (2007)** focused on the viewpoints of women on human rights. He talks about the present and potential futures for women's rights. International human rights for women are the main topic of the study. Despite being mentioned in the constitutions, human rights are not always strictly upheld. The analysis sheds insight on the state's obligation to protect these laws. All women experience domestic violence in some level domestic abuse should be regulated using International norms.

In light of the foregoing debate it is evident that while numerous studies have been conducted on women human rights in India since the country's independence with varying objectives, there remains need for additional research on the issues surrounding women human rights especially among rural women communities. So an empirical study in this area is the need of the hour.

Main Text

Human rights are generally thought of as being the rights that every human being is born with human rights legislation, which is made up of the 1945 treaties, declarations and human rights concepts adopted under the supervision of the United Nations, serves as a legal protection of human rights. The human rights framework serves as a foundation for both legislative actions to encourage institutional change and initiatives to build consensus around the principles and standards they stand for. Human rights are viewed as those fundamental, unalienable rights necessary for living as a human. The necessity to defend individuals from the abuse of the state power led to the creation of human rights. In order to uphold human rights generally and women's rights specifically, International law has established several norms. For the purpose of upholding human rights, it has established human rights institutions. The preamble of the United Nations Charter reiterates belief in fundamental human rights, in the worth and dignity of the human person, in the equality of men and women and in the rights of all nations, great and little.

According to Davidson (1993) "The concept of human rights is closely connected with the protection of individual from the exercise of State, Government or authority in certain areas of their lives, it is also directed towards the creation of social conditions of the state where individuals are to develop to their fullest potential."

According to UN, human rights are fundamental rights that all people have regardless of their race, gender, nationality, ethnicity, language, religion or any other status. A few examples of human rights are the freedom from slavery and torture, the right to life and liberty, and the freedom of speech, the right to a job and an education and a host of others. These rights are universal and unalienable.

Origin and Development of Human Rights in India

According to Nagendra Singh, the third century B.C. Buddhist teaching of non-violence in thought and deed "is a humanitarian doctrine per excellence." there were similar beliefs in Jainism as well. The Gita declares that God is fond of "him who has no ill will towards

any being, who is friendly and compassionate, who is free from egoism and self-sense, who is even-minded and pleasure and patient." Additionally, it states that the attributes that a good human being should possess non-violence, honesty freedom from anger, renunciation, and aversion to finding fault as well as tenderness, modesty and steadiness are representations of divinity. The history of ancient Bharat demonstrates unequivocally that ancient Hindu and Islamic civilizations and European Christian civilizations both uphold basic human rights. The prophet Mohammed Akber and Ashoka are inextricably linked to the history of human rights.

Acknowledging the Notion of Human Rights For Women

Women contribute illuminating insights and potent instruments to stop these discriminatory practices against women when they use the human rights concept to respect the wide range of human rights abuses that they experience. Prior to now, women's rights were viewed as women's rights but were not recognized as "human" rights. However, the concept of women's human rights inside the framework of human rights proved crucial in efforts to bring attention to these rights. Because of this, the recognition of women's human rights gives women a language to use when defining and articulating violent experiences like sexual terrorism, rape, and domestic abuse as violations of their human right to be free from torture and cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment.

Expectations regarding what can and should be done about concerns like human rights abuses rise when they are acknowledged. This human rights definition of violence against women makes it clear that states are accountable for this type of abuse. It also begs the questions of what kind of procedures are required to speed up the redress process and how to hold Governments responsible for their apathy in such cases. Women all around the world are now able to raise difficult concerns regarding the Government silence and public apathy to the pervasive violence and discrimination they face on a daily basis because to the idea of women's human rights.

The Women's Human Rights Movement

Women have always questioned why their rights are viewed as secondary to those of others, but a concerted movement to alter this perception through the application of a human rights framework gained considerable traction in the early 1990s. After the Cold War ended, there was more room for discussion and global women were able to share ideas and experiences. This led to the development of strategies for increasing the visibility of women's opinions on human rights. As women's activities expanded throughout the world during and after the UN Decade for women, an increasing number of women questioned why "women's rights" and women's lives have been regarded as less important than "human rights" and men's lives. A movement advocating for women's human rights has arisen in the last ten years, challenging narrow interpretations of human rights. It has concentrated on violence against women as a key illustration of the discrimination against women in human rights theory and practice.

The framework for women's human rights has been a vital instrument for grassroots organizing, even though it has also shown to be extremely helpful in the fight for legislative and policy changes at the Local, National and International levels. Women's human rights not only serve as a means of educating women about the various rights that their Governments are obligated to uphold, but they also serve as a framework for organizing analyses of their experiences and organizing change-related actions. Because of the numerous International human rights accords, agreements, and pledges, women have political clout and a reliable benchmark.

Meaning and Nature of Human Rights

Human Rights are exceedingly difficult to describe since there is no clear, concise understanding of what they actually entail, just like many other notions like freedom, equality, and democracy. The people, places times it has affected have changed over time. The perception varies from one level to another even within the same civilization. As times and social and economic conditions change, the true meaning continues to change as well. Now in order to comprehend human rights, it is necessary to comprehend what the term human and right mean. 'Human' refers to something that is of relates to or is of the nature of man or mankind. The term 'Right' refers to the liberties and benefits that everyone should be able to enjoy. Respect for human personality and its unquestionable value, regardless of color, ethnicity, sex, religion or other factors is the fundamental principle underlying the notion of human rights. Without entering in to definitional debates, these rights are necessary for the proper development of the human personality and for the pleasure of all people. It is important to note right away that rights

are those basic necessities of existence without which man cannot function at his best. In fact, human progress and fulfillment are facilitated by rights.

Human rights are therefore those freedoms that are fundamental to being a human and are available to everyone, regardless of gender, race, caste or religion. According to a different definition offered by David Selby, human rights are universal and belong to everyone in the world since they are a natural right that cannot be acquired through labor, purchase, inheritance or any other legal means. They are also not the result of any agreement between two parties. So, human rights are those fundamental liberties that regardless of other factors, each and every member of the human family is entitled to. Man's rights are derived from nature, according to proponents of the natural law idea. These rights come naturally and are part of who we are as people. Every person is in fact, endowed with a set of rights by nature that no authority has the power of revoke.

The following are significant conventions and declarations adopted by the UN to advance women's status:-

- i. 1952's conventional on the political rights of women.
- ii. The convention on the Nationality of Married women of 1957.
- iii. The 1967 Declaration on the Elimination of Discrimination against women.
- iv. The 1979 CEDAW (Convention to End all Discrimination against Women) convention.
- v. The 1967 Declaration on women's rights and the Elimination of violence.
- vi. The 1933 Vienna Declaration on the status of women and Human Rights.
- vii. The World Conference on women's Human Rights.
- viii. Beijing Declaration on 1995.
- ix. The United Nations Development Fund for Women (UNIFEM) is working on general justice.
- x. UNESCO, the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization.
- xi. Declaration on the Role of Women in Promoting Peace Culture.

The National Human Rights Commission fights for the protection of women's human rights, particularly in cases of domestic violence, rape, deaths in custody, cruelty, sexual harassment, and other degrading behaviors in this male dominated country. In India, a number of laws have been passed with the goal of reducing the gender pay gap and promoting women's empowerment. As fundamental rights protected by part-III of the constitution, the Indian constitution also includes a number of provisions for the respect and preservation of women's human rights.

The constitutions of Indian's Primary Provisions concerning the Rights of women are:-

In accordance with Article 14 of the Indian Constitution, no one should be denied equality before the law or equal protection under the law.

Article 15 (1):- The state is prohibited from discriminating against any citizens on the basis of their religion, race, sex, caste, or place of birth.

Article 15 (2):- No citizen shall have any limitations, liability restriction or condition with respect to:

(1-) Use of stores, public dining establishments, lodging facilities and entertainment venues; or

(2-) Utilization of wells, tanks for water storage, Ghats for public bathing, roadways and public resorts that are totally or partially supported by state funds or intended for general

public use.

Article 16 (2): No citizen shall be disqualified from or subjected to discrimination in connection with any employment or office under the state on the basis of religion, race, caste, sex, descent, place of birth or residency or any combination of these factors.

The state may provide for women under Article 16 (3). It is clear that this is meant to address their unique demands due to their specific qualities as women, such as the requirement for maternity leave before or after childbirth etc. The weaker component of every community is its female population and the court should keep this in mind while interpreting and statute.

Towards women has been quite wavering and this can be seen from some of the decisions of the courts.

The important terms contained in chapter IV of the India constitution relating to the rights of women:-

Article 39: The state must focus its policies, in particular on security.

(1-) That all citizens both men and women, equally have the right to and an appropriate means of subsistence;

(2-) The both men and women are paid equally for equally hard work;

(3-) That worker's health, strength and delicate age are not compelled by economic necessity to pursue a profession that is inappropriate for their strength or age.

Article 42: The state must establish policies to ensure fair and humane working conditions and maternity leave.

Article 44: The state must work to ensure that there is a consistent civil code for all Indian citizens. In accordance with Article 51, the state shall work to promote adherence to treaty obligations and International Law in interactions between groups of people. Basic obligation is to respect women.

Article 51 (e): states that it is the responsibility of every citizen to uphold the dignity of women and to abandon practices that are disrespectful to their worth. This obligation transcends differences in religion, language, location or division.

A turning point for the advancement of Indian was marked by the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment Act of 1993. They are guaranteed a third of all elected seats and the chairmanships of both rural and urban local elected organizations. Seventy-Five thousands of the estimated one million women expected to become leaders at the local level in only these locations alone will be chairpersons.

The Essential National Laws for the Protection of Women:-

i. Immoral Traffic (Prevention Act) of 1956 Protection.

ii. Act of 1956 Banning Dowry.

iii. Act of 1971 Authority Medical Termination of Pregnancy.

iv. Indecent Representation of Women Act of 1987.

v. Act of 1990 Concerning Commission of Sati (prevention).

vi. Act Establishing National Commissions for Women 1990.

vii. Protecting Human Rights Act of 1993.

viii. Domestic Violence Protection of Women Act of 2005.

Methodology

The study aims to examine the level of knowledge regarding women's rights in the rural community. This study which is primarily empirical in character used primary and secondary data for analysis in accordance with the goal that was stated in the study. Purposive sampling was used to choose sample respondents from whom primary data were acquired through observation, interview and planned techniques. The secondary data were gathered from websites and subject books as well as from relevant journals, newspapers, magazines and articles, academic institutions, research institutes and various departments of government and non-government were surveyed.

In light of the aforementioned, the current study was conducted to investigate the awareness about human rights among rural women in Sardhana block, with a focus on Kushawali village in the Uttar Pradesh District of Meerut. The total population of Kushawali village in Sardhana block is 1785, made up of 824 females and 961 males.

Sampling

Purposive sampling was used to choose sample respondents.

Tools Used

Primary data were acquired through observation, interview and planned techniques.

Statistics Used in the Study

The current analysis of the empirical study examines the awareness of women's rights. The sample consisted of 120 respondents. Following a correct statistical analysis of the data the following findings were obtained:-

Table-1: Awareness of Human Rights among Rural Women

S. No.	Awareness about Human Rights	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	The right to receive an education	09	7.5%
2.	Right to health protection	14	11.66%
3.	Protection against discrimination based on gender	21	17.5%
4.	Understanding of political rights	08	6.66%
5.	Understanding of the property rights	05	4.16%
6.	Defense against sexual abuse and Eve-related taunting	12	10%
7.	The right to a dignified life	07	5.8%
8.	Freedom of choice	10	8.33%
9.	Women with pride	13	10.83%
10.	Proper behavior from the family, the state, and in society	11	9.16%
11.	Sense of equality in the families and in society	06	5.0%
12.	Knowledge of reservations in local self-governance aids the women in making decisions	04	3.33%

Findings

The table above demonstrates that 09 respondents (7.5%) out of 120 respondents were aware about the right to receive an education, 14 respondents (11.66%) out of 120 respondents have knowledge about the Right to health protection, 21 respondents (17.5%) out of 120 respondents were aware about Protection against discrimination based on gender, 08 respondents (6.66%) out of 120 respondents have knowledge about political

rights in the society, 05 respondents (4.16%) out of 120 respondents knew about the property rights, 12 respondents (10%) out of 120 respondents have knowledge about the Defense against sexual abuse and Eve-related taunting, 07 respondents (5.8%) out of 120 respondents were aware about the right to a dignified life, 10 respondents (8.33%) out of 120 respondents have knowledge about the Freedom of choice, 13 respondents (10.83%) out of 120 respondents were aware about the pride regarding women, 11 respondents (9.16%) out of 120 respondents knew about that there should be a Proper behavior from the family, the state, and in society, 06 respondents (5.0%) out of 120 respondents knew about the Sense of equality in the families and in society. Only 04 respondents (3.33%) out of 120 respondents have Knowledge of reservations in local self-governance aids the women in making decisions. In response, they stated that the husbands of elected women make the majority of the decisions. As a consequence, the largest segments of the respondents (17.5%) were aware about Protection against discrimination based on gender. They said that having a girl child causes of this are poverty, dowry pressure, family pressure and protection. Every family aspires to have a son since he will inherit their possessions and no female is entitled to any inheritance.

Conclusion

Everywhere in the world, ongoing work is being done to advance women's rights and put an end to prejudice against them. Many girls and women still do not have equal opportunity to realize rights that are protected by the law, even after the Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW) was adopted thirty years ago. Women frequently lack the right to inherit land, equal status and education. The additional problems include early marriage, mobility restrictions, human trafficking and social marginalization. All women regardless of their socio-economic condition should have access to the rights and protections. In addition, unless women are aware of these rights and assert them, they are not automatically granted by legal provisions. As a result of these rights, both men and women have responsibilities that they should uphold. It is time for society to reconsider how it views women and to think outside of the patriarchal framework. Women especially, in rural communities should receive psychological stability, assistance and counseling in order to understand themselves more realistically and progressively and to value themselves as women. The government should provide special training programs and financial aid to assist rural women in starting modest cottage industries and achieving financial independence. Globally, there has been improvement in women's educational rates and in many nations, girls and young women outnumber and outperform males. These developments have not yet resulted in greater equity in the workplace, in politics, in families or in interpersonal interactions.

In conclusion, it can be argued that even when women are aware of their rights, policies, and programs, they still do not feel equal in the home or in society and are terrified of their husbands. Women did not feel like they had equal standing in their families and in society. When making decisions in the family, they are not consulted. Women in rural areas are less educated, socially, economically and legally disadvantaged and they are less aware of their rights. There is an urgent need to educate people in rural areas and about their rights, government services and programs for improving their status that are specifically for women. It is imperative that women understand their rights and exercise caution. India's women are its present and its future. Women are now in the twenty-first century are in no way inferior to males because they have achieved tremendous success in every profession and have improved lifestyles. Though Government efforts, women in rural areas are becoming aware little by little. Considering the study's conclusions, suggest a few of the following ideas. It's important for women to embrace their gender. To differentiate between right and wrong, women should foster understanding. Working women should always have their family situations in mind. After receiving unusually high praise, women should not explode emotionally. Simply finish it. Each and every person should have positive and growing attitude as a member of the human family. The status of women in society and the family should be improved by Government and Non-Governmental organizations working at the local level. Despite Government efforts, women living in rural areas will first have to become aware of their rights. Only then will more positive changes be seen in the society, because until women themselves become aware of their rights, these types of discussions will continue to happen in the society. Thus, there is more need for women's awareness. In order to educate women about their human rights, action and policy must be taken also. A program of education on women's rights must be developed for women, particularly in rural areas in order to enhance the knowledge more and more.

Suggestions for the future Study There are serious issues with the responsibility of equal treatment and proper respect for women within the current human rights regime because women are defined in most human rights instruments in terms of their child-bearing and household responsibilities, and the family which is frequently considered a platform of violence, injustice and oppression for many women's rights continues to be described as the primary unit of society. This study is particularly important since it offers important data on the degree of knowledge about rights among rural women.

References

1. Ahuja, R. 1998: "Violence against Women", New Delhi; Rawat Publications

2. Bunch, Charlotte 1997: "The Intolerable Status Quo: Violence against Women and Girl", The Progress of Nations, New York: UNICEF
3. Burns, John F. 1998: "Though Illegal Child Marriage is Popular in Part of India", The New York Times, May 11
4. Bhatt, S. 2010: "Women and Human Rights", New Delhi; Alter Publishing House
5. Charlotte, Bunch & Samantha, Frost 2000: "Women's Human Rights: An Introduction", published in Routledge International Encyclopaedia of Women: Global Women's Issues and Knowledge, Routledge
6. Davidson, S. 1993: "Human Rights", Philadelphia; Philadelphia Open University Press
7. Desai, Sonalde 1994: "Gender in Equalities and Demographic Behavior: India", New York: The Population Council, Inc.
8. Nagendra, Singh 1986: "Enforcement of Human Rights", Calcutta: Eastern Law House Pvt. Ltd., 7
9. Radhakrishnan, S. 1958: "The Bhagavadgita", (Trans.), (London: George Allen and Unwin) 276
10. Rastogi, R. 2007: "Women and Human Rights", New Delhi, Sumit Enterprises
11. Roy, A. 2003: "Human Rights of Women", New Delhi; Rajat Publications
12. R. Wallace and O Martin-Ortega 2013: "International Law", Seventh Edition, (London: Sweet and Maxwell), pp: 240
13. Sammiah, M. & Mahavi, K. 2005: "Rights of Unorganized Women Workers", Journal of Social Welfare, May, 3-6
14. Sangeeta, Sinha 2011: "Women's Rights: Tunisian Women in the Workplace", Journal of International Women's studies, vol. 12 (3), pg. no.185-200
15. Yogesh, K. Tyagi 1981: "Third World Response to Human Rights", Indian Journal of International Law, Vol.21, No.1, (January-March), 120-121
16. Chamber's Twentieth Century Dictionary, P.468
17. Longman, Dictionary of Contemporary English, P.1221
18. Suresh Kumar Soni, Human Rights: Concept, Issues, Emerging Problems, P.14
19. Tapan Biswal, Human Rights, Gender and Environment, P.44
20. Suresh Kumar Soni, Op. Cit., P.139
21. <https://www.un.org/en/sections/issues-depth/human-rights/>
22. Alexander Hamilton, The Federalist 22 US (Scottish-born) lawyer & politician (1755-1804)
23. www.wwda.org.au/whrintro1.pd
24. www.google.com